

Potential - Force and Two Component Quantum Plane Wave $\exp(ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 7, 2020

In quantum mechanics, a free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$. It has often been noted that $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ yields equal probability for any point x . In classical mechanics, one might argue that a constant real number suffices. The form $\exp(ipx)$ is also identical to the classical electromagnetic expression associated with light (i.e. a photon). In this note, we wish to begin with the idea of an ensemble of momenta at x using a real probability $f(p,x)$ and create a conservation of energy equation i.e. $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$. This equation may be differentiated to yield a force equation with $d f(p,x)/dx$. If one argues that $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ should appear in such an equation, one has a link between $d f(p,x)/dx$ and $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. One finds that $f(p,x)$, which we assume to be the same for p and $-p$ so that $pf(p,x) - pf(-p,x) = 0$ as in classical statistical mechanics, may be generalized to $f(p,x) + i g(p,x)$ with $g(p,x)$ linked to $d f(p,x)/dx$ and $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$.

In other words, quantum mechanics includes two components, one associated with $V(x)$ and $\langle p^2/2m \text{ at } x \rangle$ and another with $F(x)$ and $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. The Bohm Aharonov effect seems to justify such an approach because one may have $V(x)$ non-zero and $F(x)$ zero and still have physical effects, thus a potential $V(x)$ and $F(x)$ may both have separate physical consequences. Using $\cos(px)$ and $i \sin(px)$ seems to track these two separate consequences through the separate consequences of $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle p^2/2m \text{ at } x \rangle$. For a classical particle, p becomes p^2 by squaring so the two do not need to be treated with two separate "dimensions" i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $i \sin(px)$.

In this note, we try to obtain the form $\exp(ipx)$ from the more general $\exp(i \Theta(x,p))$ without resorting to the form $\exp(ipx)$ of a photon in classical electromagnetism and also consider an interpretation.

$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$

Quantum mechanics is said to be a statistical theory, so it seems one may begin with a momentum ensemble at x , just as in classical statistical mechanics. One may introduce a positive real conditional probability $f(p,x)$ and write:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m a(p) f(p,x)] / [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) f(p,x)] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Let } W = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) f(p,x)]$$

Assume $f(p,x) = f(-p,x)$ i.e. that there is no preference to have p or $-p$. Then, $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = 0$ just as in classical statistical mechanics.

Given ((1)), one may differentiate (d/dx) to obtain an equation involving force:

$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p/2m a(p) df/dx] / W$

$$- [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p/2m a(p) f] [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p/2m a(p) df/dx] / [WW] = F(x) \quad ((2))$$

In both ((1)) and ((2)), there exists the notion of $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$, but no notion of $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$, an average which exists. In classical statistical mechanical equilibrium, $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = 0$ even if a force is present, but here a comparison is being made with classical mechanics.

Thus, one may postulate that:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p/2m a(p) df/dx] / W \text{ is proportional to } \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \quad ((3))$$

This links df/dx to $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. Now there are two averages $\langle p/2m \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and two probability distributions $f(p,x)$ and $df(p,x)/dx$ which is a departure from classical statistical mechanics.

Next, consider that a quantum particle with a fixed p is represented by a function of p and x , but at the same time must have equal probability to be at any x point. This may be satisfied by using complex variables i.e.:

$$W(x) = R(x) \exp(i \text{ Theta}(x,p)) \text{ with } W^*(x)W(x) = 1 \text{ forcing } R(x) = 1$$

$$\text{Thus, one has a two dimensional situation with } \cos[\text{ Theta}(x,p)] \text{ and } i \sin[\text{ Theta}(x,p)]. \quad ((4))$$

If one tries to map ((4)) into ((3)) then:

$$\cos[\text{ Theta}(x,p)] \rightarrow f(p,x) \text{ and } \sin[\text{ Theta}(x,p)] \rightarrow df(p,x)/dx \quad ((5))$$

Furthermore $df(p,x)/dx$ should be proportional to p if ((3)) is to hold. A solution to ((5)) is:

$$\cos[\text{ Theta}(x,p)] = \cos(px) \text{ and } \sin[\text{ Theta}(x,p)] = \sin(px) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ takes the form of a relative conditional probability for a constant p . $\cos(px)$ is associated with $p/2m$ and $V(x)$ and $i \sin(px)$ with $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and force. One may note that $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ for a bound particle is purely imaginary. In this scenario, one does not have to rely on the form $\exp(ikx)$ taken from classical electromagnetism which describes a photon.

It is not surprising that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are out of phase by $3.14/2$. This is in keeping with the action of d/dx . What is more surprising is that one has to keep track of "two dimensions" related to $V(x)$ and $F(x)$ because both can be associated with physical results i.e. interference patterns etc. If one sets $W(x)$ to an even function $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \cos(px)$, it may appear as only one component i.e. $\cos(px)$ appears, but dW/dx brings in the second i.e. $\sin(px)$, thus both are present.

Case of a Free Quantum Particle

It is argued above that the form $\exp(ipx)$ arises through analysis of a region containing a potential. The stochastic potential knocks a particle from one $\exp(ipx)$ to another. The two components $\cos(px)$ and $i\sin(px)$ are linked through d/dx which is introduced through Force = $-d/dx V(x)$.

A free particle does not move through a region containing a force or a potential. For such a particle, d/dx behaves as a translation operator i.e.

$$dx \frac{d}{dx} (\exp(ipx)) = dx ip \exp(ipx) = dx p (\sin(px) - i \cos(px)).$$

$$\text{Consider: } \sum_{p,-p} \langle pp \text{ at } x+dx \rangle = 2 \langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle + 2 dx pp (p \sin(px)) \quad ((7))$$

The second term on the RHS is $2 dx pp \sin(px)$ which is pp multiplied by $p \sin(px)$ which is the average momentum flux for $p,-p$. The flux is shifted by $3.14/2$ ($\cos(px)$ to $\sin(px)$) so $\langle pp \rangle$ changes in an interesting manner. What is perhaps more unusual is:

$$\sum_{p,-p} \langle p \text{ at } x + dx \rangle = 2i (p \sin(px) - dx pp \cos(px)) \quad ((8))$$

In such a case, the $p/-p$ average momentum flux changes by $2i dx pp \cos(px)$ i.e. it changes according to a term proportional to the average kinetic energy (for $p/-p$) or as momentum flux of p with the probability $\sin(px)$ phase shifted to $\cos(px)$. Furthermore, both $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle pp \rangle$ change in a periodic manner i.e. as $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. This is wave-type motion (i.e. sinusoidal motion), but here it is applied to conditional probability.

It may also be noted that at low values of $pp \cos(px)$ $p \sin(px)$ takes on a large value and vice versa. For a bound state, average momentum is purely imaginary, whereas $pp \cos(px)$ is directly linked to average classical motion (i.e. to $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$). Thus, it is almost as if kinetic energy (associated with classical motion with a prms proportional to $\sqrt{KE_{ave}(x)})$ "diminishes" at certain x values at which imaginary p average (which does not exist in classical statistical mechanics) peaks. This, it seems, has led to interpretations of zitterbewegung spiral type motion. Here, however, these ideas are being applied to conditional probability and averages $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$, $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and not necessarily to actual motion. It may also be noted that for the case of a quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls, $pp \cos(pave x)$ being low is also equivalent to $P(x) KE_{ave}(x) = W(x)W(x) pave pave \cos(pave x) / W(x)$ being low where $W(x) = A \cos(pave x)$. Thus, it is not just "average kinetic energy" being low for some x , but spatial density as well in that example.

Finally, it may also be noted that conservation of $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ (which is directly linked to classical mechanics) is not the full picture in quantum mechanics. In the Bohm Ahranov effect, a free particle may experience no force, retain its constant p and still obtain a phase.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this note we begin with the assumption of conditional probability for a free particle of the form $R(x) \exp(i \Theta(x,p))$ with $R(x)=1$ and attempt to show that $\Theta(x,p) =$

px . We also argue that the two dimensional form $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ is linked to equations for $V(x)$ and force which become linked to $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.